

IMPLEMENTATION OF HUMAN RIGHTS INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION AND FOREIGN POLICY DIRECTIONS OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

Iminova Dilbarxon Mannobovna

Senior lecturer at Andijan State University.
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Annatation: this article talks about the implementation of cooperation of human rights and the implementation of the foreign policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the articles of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: politics, foreign policy, human rights, external function, Constitutional Law, internal function.

There is an internal and external function of any state, which rnasala is widely studied in the science of “theory of State and law”. The external function of the state, in turn, creates the need to conduct foreign policy. Especially in the current era of “globalization”, the conduct of proper foreign policy remains an extremely important task of the state. It is aimed at the foreign policy of any state, ensuring the security of the country, achieving the well-being of the people, finding its rightful place in the world community.

Article 17 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that “the Republic of Uzbekistan is a full-fledged subject of international relations”, as well as the second part of this article states that “the Republic can form alliances, enter and secede from the Commonwealth and other interstate structures in order to ensure the highest interests, well-being and security of the state, the people”. This provided a legal framework for Uzbekistan's full membership in the world's most prestigious international organizations and for its comprehensive recognition by the international community and rapid penetration into international political, economic and cultural relations.

Uzbekistan achieved its status as a full member of international relations only by declaring its independence on August 31, 1991. In the Constitutional Law of Uzbekistan “on the foundations of State independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan”, adopted on November 18, 1991, the main basis of our independence was legally strengthened.

Foreign policy and international activities of the Republic of Uzbekistan are based on the norms and principles of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the legislation of the Republic regulating foreign policy, legislation in the military sphere, the principles and goals of the UN and the OSCE, as well as the obligations of Uzbekistan arising from international treaties.

Representatives of the corresponding group also participate in this process. Under this term, government activities are often understood. politics is associated with the relationship between various socio-political institutions, social strata, strata and groups. Its essence is organized by the forms of state power, its implementation and management. Politics broadly expresses the priorities of the political system of society, political life, state power, its internal and external activities, the attitude of political organizations and movements to power, the implementation of political interests in its management. Accordingly, the views of fair and

unfair, impartial and nonlinear, humane or contrary to human interests, democratic and authoritarian policies can be observed in management.

Education policy refers to the general course of each state in international relations. Foreign policy is closely related to domestic policy, which determines the course of foreign policy on the basis of its internal interests. For example, one state develops economic relations with the outside world, the other with political and Economic, the third with material and art, and the fourth with the field of sports. Foreign policy determines the purpose and objectives of the implementation of this selected course, the means, forms and methods of their implementation.

Article 17 (2) of the Constitution of Uzbekistan states that "the Republic may form alliances, enter into and secede from the Commonwealth and other interstate entities in order to ensure the supreme interests, welfare and security of the state, the people".

Article 2 of the law "on the basic principles of foreign political activity of the Republic of Uzbekistan" also states that "in accordance with the Constitution of Uzbekistan, the state of Uzbekistan, its people can form alliances, enter and secede from the Commonwealth and other interstate structures in pursuit of higher interests, well-being and security".

The law "on approval of the concept of foreign political activity of the Republic of Uzbekistan", adopted on September 10, 2012, has caused great resonance in the international community

Foreign policy and international activities of the Republic of Uzbekistan include the norms and principles of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the law on international treaties of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the law on defense, the military doctrine of the Republic of Uzbekistan, other laws, principles and objectives of the United Nations and the Organization of security and cooperation in Europe, it is also based on obligations arising from international treaties and agreements of the Republic of Uzbekistan ratified by the Supreme Assembly of the Republic of Uzbekistan . But this law expired on September 14, 2012.

Uzbekistan, first of all, pursues its long-term national interests, which are the main value and principle in the foreign policy of our country: about its distance from various military-political blocs and alliances; about its strict position on the protection of sovereignty and territorial integrity, and about the non-establishment of military bases of foreign states on its territory; clearly states its principles

Uzbekistan does not allow its involvement in various conflicts that occur due to ideological principles, and the participation of our country in the foci of armed conflicts and tension on the borders with neighboring countries and territories, is a staunch supporter of good neighborliness, the settlement of which occurs only in a peaceful way.

On January 20, 1992, the UN Security Council passed its resolution 737 without a vote. In it, the Security Council considered the appeal of the Republic of Uzbekistan and recommended that the General Assembly accept Uzbekistan for membership. Uzbekistan was admitted to UN membership on 2 March 1992. After that, the relations of our country with this international organization became more and more extensive. In 1993, a UN mission was opened in Tashkent. Soon specialized bodies such as the UN Development Programme, the authorized High Commissioner for Refugee Affairs, the children's fund (UNICEF), the Industrial Development Programme, The Drug Control Programme, the World Health Organization, the population settlement fund started their activities in O'zbekistan. The

president of the Republic of Uzbekistan gave a high assessment to this organization, saying that “the United Nations is a unique organization formed to discuss and solve the most important problems of all our states, regions, the entire world community.”

- Step-by-step reform of the UN Security Council, as a first step, the inclusion of Germany and Japan, which play an important role in world politics, as part of the permanent members of the Security Council;
- Expanding the powers of the secretary-general to increase agility in reacting to Global and regional threats;
- Strengthen the role and responsibility of the Security Council in the issues of the Prevention of armed conflicts, the effective use of peaceful means and mechanisms of conflict and conflict resolution, including the so-called “compulsion to peace” in the elimination of long-standing conflicts.

On the basis of the use of international experience and UN support, the following institutions for the protection of human rights are established and operate in Uzbekistan: the representative of the Supreme Assembly for Human Rights (ombudsman) (1995); the Institute for monitoring current legislation (1996); the National Center of the Republic of Uzbekistan for human rights (1996); the Center for the study of public opinion (1997). The Republic of Uzbekistan has contributed to a number of international human rights documents adopted by the UN, and the documents that make up the International Bill of human rights occupy an important place among. The Universal Declaration of human rights, which stands after the UN Charter, was ratified by Uzbekistan on September 30, 1991. The International Covenant on economic, social and cultural rights, the International Covenant on Civil and political rights, and the facultative protocol of the pact were ratified on 31 August 1995. The pact's Second Optional Protocol, aimed at abolishing the death penalty, was ratified on December 10, 2008.

You will conclude from the above information that the implementation of human rights and the foreign policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan is being protected in the International Union and to this day international knowledge in our state, Human Rights umujahan declaration, international pacts, facultative protocols, ratified. Now studying scientific heritage, socio-political activities and acquaintance youth charity of our above-stated ancestors is considered one of the main urgent objectives of the modern intellectuals.

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